

Grain Boundary and Dislocation Mediated Deformation Mechanisms in Nanocrystalline Metals

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Abstract

Nanocrystalline metals performance of defects and mechanisms of plastic deformation and conventional polycrystalline are completely divergent in behavior and its performance.

This paper discusses about grain boundary and dislocation mediated deformation mechanisms in nanocrystalline metals. The plots are for burger vectors of single value, Gaussian and uniform characteristics considering various parameters such as elastic constants, plasticity, loading condition and uncertainty quantification.

Keyword Terms: Grain boundary, nanocrystalline metals, deformation, Burger vectors

Introduction

Grain boundary scattering and doping impurities escalates electrical resistivity of nanocrystalline materials [1]. In stress fields of grain boundary sources and concentrators, various mechanisms of plastic deformation work including generation of deformation twins, dislocation emission from grain boundary, transformation, decay and grain boundary migration [2]. Brittle and ductile process in nanocrystalline metallic materials are inclined by their structural features such as large amounts of grain boundaries and nanoscale sizes of grains. In specific, grain boundaries serve as preferable place because of nucleation and growth; atomic

density is low and interatomic bonds are weak at grain boundaries in comparison to the grain interior [3].

Literature Review

One way to avoid overlapping grain problem is to define nanostructured metal foils by sputter deposition. The film thickness can be controlled in sputtering process. Alternatively, columnar grains can be attained, which can give some understanding in bulk deformation mechanisms [4].

Device Simulation

A simulation was performed for competing grain boundary and dislocation mediated deformation in nanocrystalline metals [5].

Grain Boundary and dislocation deformation in nanocrystalline metals with Burger Vector for Single Value

Figure 1: Illustrates Yield Stress (Pa) vs Probability for Burger vector single value.

Figure 4: Illustrates Stress-strain curves for Burger vector single value.

Figure 2: Illustrates Response (Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy) for Burger vector single value

Figure 3: Illustrates Sensitivity (Sensitivity vs Parameters) for Burger vector single value

TABLE 1
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR BURGER VECTOR AS SINGLE VALUE

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Value
1	Burger Vector	Single Value
2	Burger Vector	0.25nm
3	d1	32

TABLE 2
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR ELASTIC CONSTANTS FOR BURGER VALUE AS SINGLE VALUE

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Value
1	Source	Custom
2	Young's modulus	Gaussian
3	Deviation	10GPa
4	Poisson's ratio	Single Value
5	Poisson's ratio	0.3

TABLE 3
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR PLASTICITY FOR BURGER VALUE AS SINGLE VALUE

SI No:	Plasticity	Value
1	Dislocation Glide: Peierl's Energy Barrier (J/m ²)	Gaussian
2	Mean	0.6
3	Deviation	0.06
4	Grain Boundary Sliding: Energy Barrier (J/m ²)	Single Value
5	Energy	0.5

Grain Boundary and dislocation deformation in nanocrystalline metals with Burger Vector Gaussian

Figure 5: Illustrates Yield Stress (Pa) vs Probability for Burger vector as Gaussian.

TABLE 4
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR LOADING CONDITIONS FOR BURGER VALUE AS SINGLE VALUE

SI No:	Loading Conditions	Value
1	Stress Scaling Factor	1.0
2	Maximum Strain	0.5

Figure 6: Illustrates Response (Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy) for Burger vector Gaussian.

TABLE 5
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR UNCERTAINTY QUALIFICATION FOR BURGER VALUE AS SINGLE VALUE

SI No:	Uncertainty Qualification	Value
1	Method	Smolyak+Polynomial Chaos with Legendre basis functions
2	Degree of polynomial expansion	1

Figure 7: Illustrates Response (Young's Modulus vs burgers) for Burger vector Gaussian.

Observations for Burger Vector as Single Value

- Maximum value for yield of stress is 1.23236e-09 @ 1.00113e+10Pa
- Response (Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy) for Burger vector single value has been plotted
- Sensitivity is 4.58116e+08 @ Young's Modulus and 1.94019e+09 @ Peierls Energy
- Highest peak for stress-strain curves are 0.2% offset line 1.55115e+10Pa @0.124662 and interpolated 1.17234e+10Pa @ 0.124662

Figure 8: Illustrates Response (Young’s Modulus vs Peierls Energy) for Burger vector Gaussian.

Figure 10: Illustrates Stress-Strain curves for Burger vector Gaussian

Figure 9: Illustrates Response (Burgers vs Peierls Energy) for Burger vector Gaussian

Figure 9: Illustrates Sensitivity (Sensitivity vs Parameters) for Burger vector Gaussian

TABLE 6
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR BURGER VECTOR AS GAUSSIAN

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Value
1	Burger Vector	Gaussian
2	Mean	0.25nm
3	Deviation	0.001nm
4	d1	32

TABLE 7
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR ELASTIC CONSTANTS FOR BURGER VALUE AS GAUSSIAN

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Value
1	Source	Custom
2	Young’s modulus	Gaussian
3	Mean	200GPa
4	Deviation	10GPa
5	Poisson’s ratio	Single Value
6	Poisson’s ratio	0.3

TABLE 8
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR PLASTICITY FOR BURGER VALUE AS GAUSSIAN

SI No:	Plasticity	Value
1	Dislocation Glide: Peierl's Energy Barrier (J/m ²)	Gaussian
2	Mean	0.6
3	Deviation	0.06
4	Grain Boundary Sliding: Energy Barrier (J/m ²)	Single Value
5	Energy	0.15

TABLE 9
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR LOADING CONDITIONS FOR BURGER VALUE AS GAUSSIAN

SI No:	Loading Conditions	Value
1	Stress Scaling Factor	1.0
2	Maximum Strain	0.5

TABLE 10
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR UNCERTAINTY QUALIFICATION FOR BURGER VALUE AS GAUSSIAN

SI No:	Uncertainty Qualification	Value
1	Method	Smolyak+Polynomial Chaos with Legendre basis functions
2	Degree of polynomial expansion	1

Observations for Burger Vector as Gaussian

- Maximum value for yield of stress is 1.20046e-09 @ 1.00175e+10Pa
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy for Burger vector has value between 9.80 to 9.90
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy has been plotted
- Response of Burgers vs Peierls Energy has value of 9.5
- Sensitivity is 2.18971e+08 @ burgers, 4.58116e+08 @ Young's Modulus and 1.94019e+09 @ Peierls Energy
- Highest peak for stress-strain curves are 0.2% offset line 1.55115e+10Pa @ 0.124662 and interpolated 1.17234e+10Pa @ 0.124662

Grain Boundary and dislocation deformation in nanocrystalline metals with Burger Vector Uniform

Figure 11: Illustrates Yield Stress (Pa) vs Probability for Burger vector uniform.

Figure 12: Illustrates Response (Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy) for Burger Vector Uniform.

Figure 13: Illustrates Response (Young's Modulus vs burgers) for Burger Vector Uniform.

Figure 14: Illustrates Response (Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy) for Burger Vector Uniform

Figure 15: Illustrates Response (Burgers vs Peierls Energy) for Burger Vector Uniform.

Figure 16: Illustrates Sensitivity (Sensitivity vs Parameters) for Burger Vector Uniform.

Figure 17: Illustrates Stress-Strain curves for Burger Vector Uniform.

TABLE 11
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR BURGER VECTOR AS UNIFORM

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Value
1	Burger Vector	Uniform
2	Min	0.24nm
3	Max	0.26nm
4	d1	32

TABLE 12
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR ELASTIC CONSTANTS FOR BURGER VALUE AS UNIFORM

SI No:	Simulation Specifications	Value
1	Source	Custom
2	Young's modulus	Gaussian
3	Mean	200GPa
4	Deviation	10GPa
5	Poisson's ratio	Single Value
6	Poisson's ratio	0.3

TABLE 13
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR PLASTICITY FOR BURGER VALUE AS UNIFORM

SI No:	Plasticity	Value
1	Dislocation Glide: Peierl's Energy Barrier (J/m ²)	Gaussian
2	Mean	0.6
3	Deviation	0.06
4	Grain Boundary Sliding: Energy Barrier (J/m ²)	Single Value
5	Energy	0.15

TABLE 14
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR LOADING
CONDITIONS FOR BURGER VALUE AS UNIFORM

SI No:	Loading Conditions	Value
1	Stress Scaling Factor	1.0
2	Maximum Strain	0.5

TABLE 15
SIMULATION NOMENCLATURE FOR UNCERTAINTY
QUALIFICATION FOR BURGER VALUE AS GAUSSIAN

SI No:	Uncertainty Qualification	Value
1	Method	Smolyak+Polynomial Chaos with Legendre basis functions
2	Degree of polynomial expansion	1

Observations for Burger Vector as Uniform

- Maximum value for yield stress is $1.02393e-09$ @ $1.00066e+10\text{Pa}$
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy has been plotted
- Response of Young's Modulus vs burgers is between 9.4 and 10.2
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy has value between 9.5 and 10.0
- Response of burgers vs Peierls Energy has value between 8.5 and 9.5
- Sensitivity is $4.58116e+08$ @ Young's Modulus, $6.92486e+08$ @ burgers, and $1.94019e+09$ @ Peierls Energy
- Highest peak for stress-strain curves are 0.2% offset line $1.55115e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662 and interpolated $1.17234e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662

Results

Results for Burger Vector as Single Value

- Maximum value for yield of stress is $1.23236e-09$ @ $1.00113e+10\text{Pa}$
- Response (Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy) for Burger vector single value has been plotted
- Sensitivity is $4.58116e+08$ @ Young's Modulus and $1.94019e+09$ @ Peierls Energy

- Highest peak for stress-strain curves are 0.2% offset line $1.55115e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662 and interpolated $1.17234e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662

Results for Burger Vector as Gaussian

- Maximum value for yield of stress is $1.20046e-09$ @ $1.00175e+10\text{Pa}$
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy for Burger vector has value between 9.80 to 9.90
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy has been plotted
- Response of Burgers vs Peierls Energy has value of 9.5
- Sensitivity is $2.18971e+08$ @ burgers, $4.58116e+08$ @ Young's Modulus and $1.94019e+09$ @ Peierls Energy
- Highest peak for stress-strain curves are 0.2% offset line $1.55115e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662 and interpolated $1.17234e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662

Results for Burger Vector as Gaussian

- Maximum value for yield stress is $1.02393e-09$ @ $1.00066e+10\text{Pa}$
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy has been plotted
- Response of Young's Modulus vs burgers is between 9.4 and 10.2
- Response of Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy has value between 9.5 and 10.0
- Response of burgers vs Peierls Energy has value between 8.5 and 9.5
- Sensitivity is $4.58116e+08$ @ Young's Modulus, $6.92486e+08$ @ burgers, and $1.94019e+09$ @ Peierls Energy
- Highest peak for stress-strain curves are 0.2% offset line $1.55115e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662 and interpolated $1.17234e+10\text{Pa}$ @ 0.124662

Conclusion

One of the most important application is to predict mechanical behavior of materials ahead of experiments and provide sufficient information on the atomic scale [6]. Another example specifies that inhomogeneous deformation in a nanocrystalline environment results in significant residual stresses in nanocrystals. This inner residual stress can cause strain regaining through inexpensive deformation mechanisms including dislocation reverse motion and grain boundary sliding [7].

This paper depicts visual representation of Burger Vectors for single, Gaussian and Uniform and graphs are plotted for yield stress, response of Young's Modulus vs Burgers vs Peierls Energy, response of Young's Modulus vs burgers, response of Young's Modulus vs Peierls Energy, response of burgers vs Peierls Energy, Sensitivity of Young's modulus, burgers and Peierls energy and stress-strain curves.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflict of interest as per Author's point of view.

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